

Substituent effects on the spontaneous cleavage of α -alkyl/phenyl benzyl-*gem*-dichlorides in aqueous solution

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Abstract : The solvolysis reactions of α -alkyl/phenyl benzyl-*gem*-dichlorides in water proceed by a stepwise mechanism through α -chloro- α -alkyl/phenyl benzyl carbocation intermediates, which are captured by water with a rate constant k_s (s^{-1}) to give the corresponding carbonyl compounds as the sole detectable products.

Keyword : Solvolysis.

In continuation of our earlier work, Hammett equation was applied in the solvolysis reactions of benzyl-*gem*-dichlorides and dibromides¹. The present study deals with the application of Taft equation on the title reactions.

Results and discussion

The solvolysis reactions of α -alkyl/phenyl benzyl-*gem*-dichlorides in water at 25 °C and $I = 1.0 M$ ($NaClO_4$) gave the corresponding carbonyl compounds as the sole detectable product (99%). First-order solvolysis rate constants for these reactions in the absence of chloride ion, k_{solv} (s^{-1}) were determined by monitoring the appearance of corresponding carbonyl compounds by UV spectroscopy. The normalized rate constant ratio, k_{obsd}/k_{solv} , for α -alkyl/phenyl benzyl-*gem*-dichloride, where k_{obsd} is the observed rate constant at a given concentration of chloride ion and k_{solv} is the rate constant in the absence of added chloride ion decreased with increasing $[Cl^-]$. The chloride ion inhibition shows that the reactions of α -alkyl/phenyl benzyl-*gem*-dichlorides proceed by stepwise mechanism through the diffusonally equilibrated α -chloro- α -alkyl/phenyl benzyl carbocation that can be trapped competitively by added chloride ion and solvent water (Scheme 1; where $Y = 4-MeO$).

Scheme 1

This kind of common ion inhibition on the solvolysis rates was observed for all the starting compounds studied. The linear plot ($r = 0.999$) of the data according to eq. (1) derived for the mechanism shown in Scheme 1 gives the values of k_{Cl}/k_s and are given in Table 1.

$$\frac{k_{solv}}{k_{obsd}} = 1 + \left(\frac{k_{Cl}}{k_s} \right) [Cl^-] \quad (1)$$

The common ion inhibition of the solvolysis of the α -alkyl/phenyl benzyl-*gem*-dichlorides by added chloride ion provides classic evidence for a stepwise $D_N + A_N$ (S_N1) mechanism, with rate determining cleavage of α -alkyl/phenyl benzyl-*gem*-dichlorides to form diffusonally-equilibrated carbocation reaction intermediates which can be trapped by chloride ion and by solvent². The capture of α -chloro- α -alkyl/phenyl benzyl carbocations by added chloride ion leads to a reduction in their steady-state concentration and hence in k_{obsd} for solvolysis of the starting α -alkyl/phenyl benzyl-*gem*-dichlorides. The good fit to eq. (1), derived for the mechanism shown in Scheme 1, of the kinetic data for solvolysis of α -alkyl/phenyl benzyl-*gem*-dichlorides in the presence of increasing concentration of chloride ion shows that the reactions proceed through liberated carbocation intermediates. From the plot of k_{solv}/k_{obsd} versus $[Cl^-]$ the value of k_{Cl}/k_s was obtained for α -alkyl/phenyl benzyl-*gem*-dichloride. Absolute rate constants k_s (s^{-1}) for capture of α -chloro- α -alkyl/phenyl benzy carbocations by water were obtained from the rate constant ratios k_{Cl}/k_s (M^{-1}) for partitioning of the cations and using a value of $k_{Cl} = 5 \times 10^9 M^{-1} s^{-1}$ for the reaction of cation with Cl^- .

Table 1. Solvolysis of α -alkyl/phenyl benzyl-*gem*-dichlorides in aqueous solution at 25 °C and $I = 1.00 M$ (NaClO_4)

R	k_{solv} (s^{-1})	$k_{\text{Cl}^-}/k_{\text{s}}$ (M^{-1})	k_{s} (s^{-1})	$\Delta H_{\text{solv}}^\ddagger$ (kJ mol^{-1})	$\Delta S_{\text{solv}}^\ddagger$ $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$	$\Delta H_{\text{s}}^\ddagger$ kJ mol^{-1}	$\Delta S_{\text{s}}^\ddagger$ $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$
H	1.50×10^{-2}	2.00	2.5×10^9	18.7	-4.47	21.2	55.6
CH_3	2.50×10^{-2}	7.00	7.0×10^8	24.4	-57.2	67.9	190
CH_3CH_2	2.63×10^{-2}	10.5	4.76×10^8	97.5	-38.2	32.7	30.8
C_6H_5	2.36×10^{-2}	Could not be determined due to low solubility of the compound with increasing $[\text{Cl}^-]$		40.4	-140		

There is about 2-fold increase in k_{solv} for α -alkyl/phenyl benzyl-*gem*-dichlorides as the α -substituent R is changed from H to C_2H_5 (Table 1), which is consistent with a development of positive charge at the benzylic carbon in the rate-determining transition state for solvolysis. Replacing an α -H by α - CH_3 or by α - CH_2CH_3 transforms a primary substrate into a tertiary substrate. It is generally known that the tertiary cations are more stable than the secondary cations that are in turn more stable than the primary cations, and more stable cations form more rapidly in solution. Therefore from the Table it is clear that more stable cations formed more rapidly, more selective and less reactive towards nucleophiles i.e. in the present case with water (k_{s} values). Therefore it is evident that the electron-donating groups like CH_3 and C_2H_5 that are present in benzyl cations at α -position will stabilize the cations.

The good Taft correlation of $\log k_{\text{solv}}$ for equilibrium formation of the α -alkyl/phenyl- α -chloro benzyl carbocations from the neutral chloride ion adducts with σ^* substituent constants ($\rho_{\text{solv}} = -0.43$) which is consistent with a development of positive charge at the benzylic carbon in the rate-determining transition state for solvolysis which shows that the thermodynamic stability of

cations is sensitive to the polar effects of the substituents to a larger extent. A similar good Taft correlation is also observed for the $\log k_{\text{s}}$ for addition of water to α -alkyl/phenyl- α -chloro benzyl carbocations ($\rho_{\text{s}}^* = 1.19$). The higher value of ρ_{s}^* than the ρ_{solv}^* may be an indication that the cations are more sensitive to the substituents than the neutral chloride ion adducts.

Of particular importance are the negative sign and the magnitude of $\Delta S_{\text{solv}}^\ddagger$ values (Table 1). The negative values of entropy indicate reorganization of the solvent shell in the transition state as a result of hydration of ions.

Experimental

All experimental details were similar to those reported earlier from our laboratory¹.

References

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